

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL FACTORS IN SHAPING THE ENVIRONMENT AFFECTING THE HARMONIOUS DEVELOPMENT OF EARLY CHILDHOOD

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Abstract

A variety of social factors can affect children's development and health as an indicator of the well-being of society.

Keywords: social factors, harmonious development of early childhood

This article presents the results of a scientific sociological study in the Republic of Moldova, the reason for which was caused by the need to raise the awareness and investigate the social environment that contributes to a harmonious and prosperous childhood.

The well-being of children in the modern society arouses the interest of scientists in different scientific fields and this is conditioned by the fact that the healthy child population is the basis of the future healthy adult population, the socially safe society with a good level of life quality. Therefore, early childhood health should be perceived as an indicator of the society well-being as a whole and be regarded as a national asset. The social environment affecting a child before birth, the environment into which the child enters after birth and where its development is taking place, can have a determining influence on its health and consequently on

the overall wellbeing of its early childhood, which is the foundation for a healthy country's population. As a result, society needs more sociological research on the social environment, including social factors that affect child development, both positively and negatively. The relevance of conducting sociological research on early childhood consists in identifying the specific influence of social factors on the formation of health.

The study was conducted following the methodology of sociological research, including a basic field study, the respondents were parents of children 0-5 years old, an expert survey of doctors and kindergarten workers, establishing the health group of children 0-5 years old regarding the influence of the social environment. In the course of the work, a classification of the main social factors was developed.

Table 1.

The classification of social factors influencing the health of children aged 0 to 5 developed for this study:

Social factors	Institute of the family	Institute of early childhood care and education	Institute of health	Institute of the State
Socio-demographic	Parents' age	Age of caregivers	Age of doctors	Birth rate, marriage and divorce rates at the state level
	Child's age			
	Number of children in the family	Number of children in the group	Number of children attended by a doctor	
	Family type by composition			
Personal	Parents' education	Education of caregiver	Doctors' qualifications	Life expectancy
	Type of work	Length of service	Length of service	
	Job title			
Behavioural	Quality of care for the child	Quality of care	Quality of medical care	Government policy on early childhood
	Parent literacy	Cooperation with parents	Cooperation with parents	
	Cooperation with health staff and caregivers			
Socio-psychological	Family climate	Child's mood when attending kindergarten		Government policy in support of the psychological health of the population as a whole.
	Quality of communication with the child	Psychological Group climate		
Socio-economic	Income level in the family	Type of kindergarten private/public/public with parental grant	Type of health centre private/public	Material standard of living in the country
		Accommodation in kindergartens	Equipment of medical facilities	Migration
	Housing conditions	Nutrition quality		
Socio-cultural	Life style. Behaviour patterns in the family	Cultural and educational standards in pre-schools	Cultural patterns of health workers in the organisation of care and prevention involved in the promotion of early childhood health.	Level of culture in the country
	Attitude towards religion			
Socio-geographical	Residence in rural-urban areas	Location in rural-urban areas	rural-urban areas	Geographical position of the country in relation to neighbouring countries.

While addressing the problem of studying the social causes of health, researchers have tried to position sociology of childhood in the Republic of Moldova as a separate discipline within general sociology, with entirely new approaches to the study of different childhood problems. Thus, modern society needs new knowledge reflecting the changes in society. For example, the modern Moldovan sociologist in RM V. Reabcinschii [8, p.12] writes that the value framework of the country's population has recently changed, the population has started to value more the quality of personal life, the criteria of which are health, family, material wellbeing, peace and justice. The hope is that the

change of cultural values towards the better - the quality of personal life, health, family values - will trigger a positive inertia wave towards the well-being of early childhood as well, through the formation of a new mindset of society and the way of life of its citizens.

So far, attitudes towards children in our country, care for their well-being and its basic criteria - physical, mental and social health - remain in the perspective of our country's development at both macro- and micro-social levels. According to UNICEF research [5], in Moldova many parents consider it acceptable to beat their children and the younger the child, the more likely he or she is to be physically abused. According to the National Bureau of Statistics of the RM, 755 children

were abused in 2019. The number of street children [6, 32] was 2,111 in 2005, 4,176 in 2015 and 8,600 in 2019, of which 49.1% were children aged 7-15, i.e., of early preschool age. This shows that the number of neglected children in the country has quadrupled over these years, with very young children among them, as well as physically abused children. By the end of 2019, 1,100 children were in residential care. [2, p.169]. Based on these data alone, it must be understood that child population is in distress, unable to undergo socialisation properly, that is the way healthy children are supposed to; it is crucial to realize that the sociology of childhood is not yet seen as a general state policy that aims at the well-being of young children as the basis of a healthy population of the country.

In this paper, the motivation for studying this very child age group was the socio-physiological vulnerability of the child population, which always requires special efforts and attention on the part of society in order to maintain and nurture a healthy gene pool. The WHO stresses in its findings that "a significant proportion of the global burden of disease that can be attributed to hazards in the physical environment occurs in children under 5 years of age." [1, p.7], which confirms the need for special attention and detailed study of this age group, the period of childhood, when the foundations of health for later life are being laid and formed. The study of society with its social factors, where a child is formed and grows up, implies, along with socio-economic and socio-political processes in society, the study of socio-cultural traditions, norms and values that form adults' worldview and that can influence the proper socialization of young children, which is considered in our work as a conceptual process that plays a major role in the development of healthy personalities of early childhood.

The study was based on the principles of the International Convention for the Protection of Children, adopted by General Assembly resolution 44/25 of 1989 [4]. The results of the field study showed that a negative impact on the health of young children, manifested by high morbidity and frequent complications, in 60% is caused by conflict in the family. 56% of experts responded that family conflicts have a negative impact on the health of young children. Another negative factor contributing to high morbidity among young children is the psychological state of children during kindergarten visits, such as fatigue and unwillingness to go to kindergarten. One more negative factor identified during the survey was related to teachers who admit sick children to the group.

The study took place during the pandemic period and the pandemic factor was found to be positive in shaping children's health - during this period, teachers stopped admitting sick children into groups. The number of children attending groups was reduced, and smaller groups were formed, which had a positive effect on reducing child morbidity. 63.2% of the experts expressed an opinion about the role of doctor's qualification in the positive aspect, as well as the trust in the doctor. As for the demographic factor - in full families in official marriage there are both fully healthy children

and children who frequently get ill, so this factor cannot be called decisive, nevertheless healthy children prevail in this factor. The full family factor in unofficial marriages has a negative trend towards an increase in frequently ill children, as well as a negative trend in families after divorce. The socio-economic factor in families showed that equally sick and healthy children can be in families with different material levels, which did not confirm the generally accepted opinion. The care factor on the part of the parents - adequate nutrition, a full drinking regime, developing resistance to the cold - confirmed a positive role in the formation of good early childhood health.

Conclusion.

To summarise, the most negative factors affecting early childhood health appear to be psychological factors within the family and on the part of socialisers. When asked the open-ended question about what is needed for a child to be healthy, about 50% of respondents pointed to love. Perhaps the conclusion to be drawn from our research is that a positive attitude towards small children, a loving environment which provides the impetus for their harmonious development is essential. In 'The Art of Love', the German sociologist Erich Fromm gives a concept of what love is and what its resources are. And in a social environment, given the aspect of socialisation by adults, love is an art, which has a value for the soul. The scholar stresses that man having left the animal world cannot return back, which is in line with the concept of socialisation of young children in society. Because of their vulnerability, children need adults. The art of loving requires knowledge, he writes, and consequently understanding, both in relationships between adults and in the attitude towards the small child, respect, acceptance of expression, the peculiarity of giving is a manifestation of adulthood [2, p.56] ability to love depends on the level of development of personality, ability to give, quality of love expression, he writes can be seen in the attitude of mother towards the child. Besides material nourishment, Erich Fromm calls love spiritual nourishment, which corresponds to the research results [7, p. 83].

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